

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MEDICATION ADHERENCE AND HYPERTENSION STATUS IN PUBLIC HEALTH CENTER

Putu Dian Pratita Lestari*, Luh Oliva Saraswati Suastika** and I Putu Eka Widyadharna* **,1

*Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University, **Department of Cardiology and Vascular Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University, Sanglah General Hospital, Bali, Indonesia , ***Department of Neurology Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University, Sanglah General Hospital, Bali, Indonesia

ABSTRACT Background: In Indonesia, the burden of hypertension is still reaching the uppermost rank among all diseases. Recent data showed that only 0.7% of people diagnosed with hypertension were taking their suggested regiment of medication. **Objective:** To determine the relationship between medication adherence to hypertension status in hypertensive patients in a public health centre. **Method:** This was an analytical-observational, cross-sectional study design involving 55 patients with hypertension who attended general and geriatric outpatient clinic of Mengwi I Public Health Center, Bali, from May until September 2018. Medication adherence was assessed with the Modified Morisky Adherence Scale-8 (MMAS-8) questionnaire, and hypertension status was determined based on the medical record. Chi-square analysis used to see the relationship between hypertension status with medication adherence, current anti-hypertensive therapy, changes in therapy, number of visits, comorbid diseases, duration of hypertension, exercise habits, and age. **Result:** Most subjects were women (61.8%) with an average age of 62.9 ± 9.9 years. Of all subjects, 47.3% were non-adherent, and 58.2% had uncontrolled hypertension. Only 25.5% patient had more than four consecutive visits. Mean duration of hypertension was 2.4 ± 1.9 years. There was a significant relationship between medication adherence and the amounts of visits with hypertension status ($P < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** There was a significant relationship between medication adherence and the amounts of visits with hypertension status. Effective and comprehensive treatment of hypertension should have its imperative efforts by the patient combined with supporting health system, to receive an early diagnosis, pharmacological treatment as well as non-pharmacological management, and healthy lifestyle advice given by the physicians.

KEYWORDS hypertension, adherence, visits, public health centre

Introduction

Hypertension, as-so-called a global silent killer, is a disease that needs to be watched out because at any time it can become an unexpected killer. In Indonesia, the burden of hypertension is still reaching the uppermost rank among all diseases. The national hypertension prevalence based on Riskesdas 2013 was 25.8% [1]. Based on these data from 25.8% of people who had hypertension only one-third of them was diagnosed [2]. Recent data showed that only 0.7% of people diagnosed with hypertension were taking their suggested regiment of medication [3-4]. Most hypertensive sufferers are unaware of suffering from hypertension or getting treatment. Target organ damage due to

Copyright © 2019 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons
DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.MedicationAdherenceandHypertension-Status-Public-Health-Center

First Received: December 20, 2018

Accepted: January 01, 2019

Manuscript Associate Editor: Ivon Ribarova (BG)

Reviews: Adnan Kaya (TR)

¹Dr I Putu Eka Widyadharna, Department of Neurology Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University, Sanglah General Hospital, Bali, Indonesia

E-mail:eka.widyadharna@unud.ac.id

Phone: +623618959800

Mobile: +62 81237872840

complications of hypertension will depend on the amount of increase in blood pressure and the length of the condition of undiagnosed and untreated blood pressure [1]. If the disease is not controlled, will attack target organs, and can cause heart attacks, strokes, kidney disorders, and blindness. From several studies, it was reported that uncontrolled hypertension could cause a seven times greater chance of stroke, six times more likely to have congestive heart failure, and three times greater heart attack [3-4].

Success in controlling high blood pressure is a joint effort between the patient and the doctor who handles it. Patient adherence is the main factor in determining the success of therapy. Adherence and good understanding in carrying out therapy can affect blood pressure and prevent complications from occurring [5-6]. In addition to medication adherence, the pattern of hypertension therapy given by doctors also plays an essential role in controlling blood pressure [7]. Various studies have examined the risk factors for hypertension, and many comprehensive management guidelines have been published. However, the risk factors for uncontrolled hypertension are still lacking [5].

There are several reasons for the lack of medication adherence in hypertensive patients, including the failure to identify and deal with patients' perceptions of the disease and their beliefs about the benefits and problems of therapy, on the other hand, the nature of hypertension is mostly asymptomatic, making it difficult for patients to maintain adherence. Sometimes, patients do not understand the long-term benefits of therapy, due to either economic problems such as poverty, psychological depression, or the presence of comorbid diseases such as diabetes. Besides that, there were some factors which can be worsening such condition; inability to access and maintain contact with affordable, available and appropriate health care systems, such as the availability of insurance health, and the fear of long-term treatment side effects [7].

Public Health Center is a functional health-based organization that carries out comprehensive, integrated, equitable, acceptable and affordable health efforts for the community, with active participation from the community [8]. One indicator of a healthy family is a good adherence, means that hypertensive patients are willing to take medication regularly. Hypertension patient can routinely control and take medication at the health centre regularly. This research is very appropriate to be carried out in a community health centre because it plays a role in preventive efforts, one of which is preventing complications of hypertension through regular treatment so that the existence of this research is expected to provide input to the health centre and community as well.

This research aims to determine the relationship between medication adherence to uncontrolled hypertension to prevent complications caused by uncontrolled hypertension, to improve the quality of life of hypertensive sufferers and reduce the costs incurred from treatment due to hypertensive complications.

Methods

An analytical-observational study with cross-sectional study design was done to know if there was any association between adherence and grade of hypertension. Study was done in general and geriatric outpatient clinic of Mengwi I Public Health Center, Bali, Indonesia for four months, starting from May until September 2018. The number of the sample used in this study determined by total sampling. Sample selection was made using consecutive sampling. The inclusion criteria in this study

were the age of at least 18 years old, had minimal hypertension treatment in the last three months, and there were blood pressure readings over the previous three months, and willing to be respondents. Exclusion criteria include incomplete medical record data, subjects having hearing or speaking disorders. The independent variables in this study were the level of medication adherence, age, sex, comorbid disease, duration of hypertension, visits to health centres, sports, changes in therapy, and current therapy.

Uncontrolled hypertension is defined as at least two blood pressure measurements $\geq 150 / 90$ mmHg is recorded for >60 years patients without diabetes mellitus type 2 (DMT2) or chronic kidney disease (CKD) and $140/90$ mmHg for patients with DMT2 or CKD or those younger than 60 years. Controlled hypertension is defined if there were at least two blood pressure measurements $<150/90$ mmHg for patients aged <60 years without DMT2 or CKD and $<140/90$ mmHg for patients with DMT2 or CKD or those younger than 60 years.

The subject will be explained about the research flow and signed the consent sheet for participation in the study. Subjects will be interviewed about essential characteristics, adherence with medication based on the MMAS-8 questionnaire, and consumption of foods containing salt with the SQFFQ questionnaire. MMAS-8 questionnaire in the Indonesian language, specifically made a scale to measure adherence to taking an eight-item drug containing statements that showed the frequency of forgetfulness in taking medication, intentionally stopping taking medication without the doctor's knowledge, the ability to control himself to keep taking medication. MMAS-8 questionnaire was used to measure the level of adherence of hypertensive patients. The MMAS-8 questionnaire consists of 8 questions, with seven questions with the results of the answers yes or no, where the answer yes has a score of 1 and the answer no has a score of 0. While the question number 8 has several answer choices, never has a score of 1; occasionally has a score of 0.75; sometimes has a score of 0.5; usually has a score of 0.25; and always has a score of 0. To determine the level of adherence obtained from the total score included in the adherence (total score ≥ 6), and non-adherence category (total score <6) [6]. Regular exercise was defined by exercise at least three times a week within 30 minutes or more; or if the respondent does certain sports at least three times a week with a minimum of 30 minutes. Hypertension status, therapy for hypertension is currently obtained from medical record data. Data were analyzed with SPSS version 20 for Windows.

Univariate tests were conducted to see the frequency distribution and proportion of the research variables presented in the form of numbers and tables. Bivariate analysis is intended to see the relationship between dependent variables, including hypertension status with variable medication adherence, anti-hypertensive therapy patterns, number of visitors, comorbid, duration of hypertension, and exercise habits and age using Chi-Square test. The analysis was significant if $p < 0.05$

Results

The study performed in the General and Geriatric Outpatient Clinic of Mengwi I Public Health Center, Bali, Indonesia from June to September 2018. The collection of the subject was done by answering the prepared questionnaire.

There was a total of 55 subjects included in our study; most subjects were elderly with an average age of 62.9 ± 9.9 years, 61.8% are women. Most of the respondents (78.2%) were still

Table 1 Characteristics of Subjects

Variable		Result
Age		62.9 ± 9.9 years
Gender	Male	21 (38.2%)
	Female	34 (61.8%)
Marriage Status	Married	43 (78.2%)
	Widowed	12 (21.8%)
Body Mass Index	Normal	40 (72.7%)
	Overweight	8 (14.5%)
	Obesity	7 (12.7%)
Comorbidities	Yes	17 (30.9%)
	No	38 (69.1%)
Duration of Hypertension		2.4 ± 1.9 years
Visits to Public Health Center	Often	14 (25.5%)
	Seldom	41(74.5%)
Exercise	Regular	12 (21.8%)
	Unregular	43 (78.2%)
Salt consumption		1540.5 ± 257.7 mg
First-prescribed antihypertension	Amlodipine	26 (47.3%)
	Captopril	26 (47.3%)
	Combination	4 (7.3%)
Current antihypertension		
Single		45(81.8%)
	Amlodipine	31 (68.6%)
	Captopril	12 (26.6%)
	Ramipril	1 (2.2%)
	Irbesartan	1 (12.2%)
Combination		10 (18.2%)
	Combination of Amlodipine-Captopril	9 (90%)
	Combination of Amlodipine-HCT	1 (10%)
Changes in pharmacological therapy		
Yes		22 (40%)
	Any addition of dose/frequency	4 (7.3%)
	Any addition of another group of drug	8 (14.5%)
	Any changes with another groupof drug	6 (10.9%)
	Any reduction of dose/frequency	4 (7.3%)
No		33 (60%)

Table 2 Correlation between Status of Hypertension and Independent Variables.

Variable	Hypertension Status		P
	Controlled	Uncontrolled	
Age	65.56 ± 6.2 year	61.0 ± 11 year	0.10
Gender			1.99
Women	17 (73.9%)	17 (53.1%)	
Men	6 (26.1%)	15 (46.9%)	
Comorbidities			1.00
Yes	7 (30.4%)	10 (31.3%)	
No	16 (69.6%)	22 (68.8%)	
Duration of Hypertension			0.34
<3 years	12 (52.2%)	22 (68.8%)	
≥ 3 years	11 (47.8%)	10 (31.3%)	
Visits to Public Health Center			0.04
Often	11 (47.8%)	3 (9.4%)	
Seldom	12 (52.2%)	29 (90.6%)	
Exercise			0.75
Regular	6 (26.1%)	6 (18.8%)	
Unregular	17 (73.9%)	26 (81.3%)	
Current therapy			0.16
Single	21 (91.3%)	24 (75.0%)	
Combination	2 (8.7%)	8 (25.0%)	
Adherence of therapy			<0.001*
Adherence	22 (95.7%)	7 (21.9%)	
Non-adherence	1 (4.3%)	25 (78.1%)	

* stastically significant

married and had a spouse.

As many as 72.7% of our subjects had normal body mass index, only 12.7% were obese, and 14.5% was overweight. Of all subjects, only 17 people (30.9%) had a comorbid disease which was DMT 2, and all took medications for DMT2. The mean duration of hypertension was 2.4 ± 1.9 years. There were 41.8% of patients with controlled hypertension status and 58.2% with uncontrolled hypertension. Based on the results of the study, 47.3% of the subjects were non-adherence, and 52.7% were adherence to treatment. In this study, only 21.8% of subjects had regular exercise. The average salt consumption was 1540.5 ± 257.7 mg.

Amlodipine is the most frequently given antihypertensive therapy (47.3%) by general physicians working in this outpatient clinic. Only as many as 40% of our samples had changes in anti-hypertensive therapy over time, with 14.5% of additives in other groups such as captopril. In this study, there was a significant association between medication adherence and visits to health centres with hypertension status ($P < 0.05$). Other variables such as age, sex, comorbid disease, duration of hypertension, exercise, and therapy are currently not related to hypertension status ($P > 0.05$).

Discussion

This cross-sectional analytical study of hypertensive subjects underscores the magnitude of the lack of awareness of hypertension and the suboptimal medication adherence in a suburban area in Bali. Nearly half of the study participants were poorly adherent to the prescribed anti-hypertensive medications following the diagnosis of hypertension.

This study had found that there was no significant relationship between exercise and the incidence of uncontrolled hypertension. This condition is possible because other variables act as stronger risk factors for uncontrolled hypertension. Based on the results of in-depth interviews, respondents are rarely doing ideal exercise (3-4 times in a week with a minimum of 30 minutes per exercise) or moderate intensity exercises, such as walking, jogging, cycling and swimming. Reason for the lacks of regular exercise included leg sore, busy with works and had no free time to do physical exercise. To control blood pressure, Mengwi I Public Health Center, Bali, Indonesia has been conducting an act of the Chronic Disease Management Program called "Program Pengelolaan Penyakit Kronis" (Prolanis), regularly once a month. The program consisted of yoga, counselling and consultation, but not all of the hypertensive patients took part in this program. This is due to a lack of patient awareness.

Based on the results of calculations using the Chi-Square test showed that there was a significant relationship between adherence to taking antihypertensive drugs and uncontrolled hypertension. The results of this study are by previous studies by E Degli et al. (2003) which states that there is a relationship between the consumption of antihypertensive drugs and the incidence of uncontrolled hypertension ($p = 0.001$). This is proportional to the number of visits to the public health centre, in which, indeed, shows a significant relationship with the status of hypertension. The MMAS-8 questionnaire used in our study gave information regarding if the patient is adherence or not in taking the drug, by evaluating medication-taking behaviour represent in question in the survey. The result of our study showed that in controlled hypertension group, most of the subjects had good adherence to the therapy, while in uncontrolled hypertension group, only 22% patients had adherence to taking

the medication given by the doctor. If they neither feel dizzy nor a headache, drugs were not consumed.

The antihypertensive drugs most often given were captopril and amlodipine and combination of captopril-amlodipine. The diuretic was rarely given as a single therapy. Among respondents who need a combination regimen, doctors add diuretics. Antihypertensive drugs were usually given for the next 5-10 days due to the national health insurance regulation. So that every ten days, the patients have to visit the public health centre to check their blood pressure to get more medication. Many patients did not routinely visit the clinic due to this particular reason and prefer to buy drugs over the counter. Limitation of days decided by doctors to prescribe antihypertensive drugs is only for 5-10 days, because of the limited number of drugs stocked in public health centre.

This study showed a significant relationship between adherence towards medication and hypertension status. If the patients have more adherence in consuming oral hypertensive agents which prescribed by their doctors, their hypertensive status would be controlled. Vrijens et al. (2012) defined adherence as a dynamic process by which patients takes their medications as prescribed, changes over time. Adherence consists of three components; initiation, implementation, and persistence, by which, each one of it represents three phases of time; non-adherence, consequences, and monitoring. Otherwise, non-adherence means when a patient neither initiates a new prescription, implement as prescribed, nor persist with the treatment given by the doctor [9]. As hypertensive status is related to cardiovascular risks and other health-related outcomes, paying attention to control it would be a worthy contribution. A study by Corrao et al. (2011) showed that persistence with antihypertensive agent significantly reduces long-term cardiovascular risk [10].

Aetiology of adherence to medications is considered as multifactorial. Addressing factors related to adherence and looking for solutions were not as easy as it seems. The first thing that needs to be considered is educational and empowerment efforts [11]. A study by Naik et al. have found that shared-decision-making style and proactive communication demonstrated significant direct effects on hypertension control in diabetic patients [12]. Self-monitoring and uptitrating of drugs by the patients may be helpful to improve blood pressure control in high cardiovascular risk patients; a study reported [13]. In this respect, home blood pressure monitoring is recommended in patients who have difficulties with their treatment and are at high risk of not staying on therapy [14]. Affordability, related to the different level of income for all countries, is an essential consideration as this is a problem for medication adherence. A recent systematic review by Nielsen et al. (2017) highlighted that non-adherence to antihypertensive medication in low- and middle-income countries were more problematic in some parts of the world. Indeed, worse hypertensive status was found. National health insurance program would be a high starting point for alleviating adherence to hypertensive medication, despite it could not interfere with individual control [15].

In this study, visits to public health centres also positively associated with hypertension status ($P < 0.05$). A visit to the health centre was used as an indicator of assessing medical use or medication adherence. Practical and comprehensive treatment of hypertension should have its important efforts by the patient, to receive an early diagnosis, pharmacological treatment as well as non-pharmacological management and advice given by the

physicians. A study in Korea revealed that the rate of visiting a medical institution was 20.9% for study subjects in their 30s, it suggested that early diagnosis of hypertension did not induce early administration of treatment as effective as it should be. Among subjects who received the antihypertensive prescription, the majority of them (98.3%) purchased the medication as well. [16].

Visits to health centres linked with the patient's motivation. Some study revealed that highly motivated patients take more responsibilities, gaining disease-specific knowledge and implementing skills they have acquired into their daily life, thus promoting self-management and facilitating effective interactions with the health care system while also encouraging engagement in healthy behaviours, including preserving their time to go to health centres [17]-[20]. Studies suggest that the alleviation of the patient's motivation is strongly associated with a variety of self-management behaviours [21].

Conclusion

Nearly half of the study participants were poorly adherent to the prescribed anti-hypertensive medications following the diagnosis of hypertension. This study also showed a significant relationship between medication adherence and the number of visits to the community health centre with hypertension status. A practical and comprehensive treatment of hypertension should have its essential efforts by the patient combined with supporting health system, to receive an early diagnosis, pharmacological treatment as well as non-pharmacological management, and healthy lifestyle advice given by the physicians.

References

1. Elperin DT, Pelter MA, Deamer RL, Burchette RJ. A Large Cohort Study Evaluating Risk Factors Associated With Uncontrolled Hypertension. *The Journal of Clinical Hypertension*. 2014.4(2): 149-154
2. Departemen Kesehatan. Survei kesehatan nasional. Laporan Departemen Kesehatan RI. Jakarta. 2013.
3. Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure (JNC). The Seventh Report of the JNC (JNC-7). *JAMA*. 2003;289(19):2560-72.
4. Rahajeng E dan Tuminah S. Prevalensi Hipertensi dan Determinannya di Indonesia. *Maj Kedokt Indon*. 2009. 59(12):580-587
5. Esposti LD, Saragoni S, Benemei S, Batacchi P, Geppetti P, Di BM, Marchionni N, Sturani A, Buda S, Esposti ED. Adherence to antihypertensive medications and health outcomes among newly treated hypertensive patients. *Clinicoecon Outcomes Res*. 2011; 3:47-54.
6. Krousel-Wood M, Holt E, Joyce C, Ruiz R, Dornelles A, Webber LS, Morisky DE. Differences in cardiovascular disease risk when antihypertensive medication adherence is assessed by pharmacy fill versus self-report: The Cohort Study of Medication Adherence among Older Adults (CoSMO). *J Hypertens*. 2015; 33(2): 412-420
7. Kaplan NM and Victor RG. 2015. *Kaplan's Clinical Hypertension*. 11th Edition. Wolters Kluwer; Philadelphia:179-193

8. Peraturan Menteri Kesehatan Republik Indonesia Nomor 39 Tahun 2016 Tentang Pedoman Penyelenggaraan Program Indonesia Sehat Dengan Pendekatan Keluarga.
9. Vrijens B, De Geest S, Hughes DA, et al. A new taxonomy for describing and defining adherence to medications. *Br J Clin Pharmacol.* 2012;73(5):691-705.
10. Corrao G., Parodi A., Nicotra F., Zambon A., Merlino L., Cesana G., et al. (2011). Better adherence to antihypertensive medications reduces cardiovascular risk. *J. Hypertens.* 29 610–618. doi:10.1097/HJH.0b013e328342ca97.
11. Burnier, M. (2017). Drug adherence in hypertension. *Pharmacological Research*, 125, 142–149. doi:10.1016/j.phrs.2017.08.015
12. Naik AD, Kallen MA, Walder A and Street RL, Jr. Improving hypertension control in diabetes mellitus: the effects of collaborative and proactive health communication. *Circulation.* 2008;117:1361-8.
- 13 McManus RJ, Mant J, Haque MS, Bray EP, Bryan S, Greenfield SM, Jones MI, Jowett S, Little P, Penaloza C, Schwartz C, Shackelford H, Shovelton C, Varghese J, Williams B and Hobbs FD. Effect of self monitoring and medication self-titration on systolic blood pressure in hypertensive patients at high risk of cardiovascular disease: the TASMIN-SR randomized clinical trial. *Jama.* 2014;312:799-808.
13. Parati G, Stergiou GS, Asmar R, Bilò G, de Leeuw P, Imai Y, Kario K, Lurbe E, Manolis A, Mengden T, O'Brien E, Ohkubo T, Padfield P, Palatini P, Pickering TG, Redon J, Revere M, Ruilope LM, Shennan A, Staessen JA, Tisler A, Waeber B, Zanchetti A and Mancia G. European Society of Hypertension practice guidelines for home blood pressure monitoring. *Journal of human hypertension.* 2010;24:779-85.
14. Nielsen J. O., Shrestha A. D., Neupane D., Kallestrup P. (2017). Non-adherence to anti-hypertensive medication in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis of 92443 subjects. *J. Hum. Hypertens.* 31 14–21. doi:10.1038/jhh.2016.31.
15. Jeong H, Kim H, Lee K, et al. Medical visits, antihypertensive prescriptions and medication adherence among newly diagnosed hypertensive patients in Korea. *Environ Health Prev Med.* 2017;22(1):10. Published 2017 Mar 17. doi:10.1186/s12199-017-0619-6.
16. Gleason-Comstock J, Streater A, Ager J, et al. Patient education and follow-up as an intervention for hypertensive patients discharged from an emergency department: a randomized control trial study protocol. *BMC Emerg Med.* 2015;15:38. Published 2015 Dec 21. doi:10.1186/s12873-015-0052-3.
17. Hibbard J, Greene J, Tusler M. Improving the outcomes of disease management by tailoring care to the patient's level of activation. *Am J Manag Care.* 2009;15(6):353–60.
18. Deen D, Lu WH, Rothschild D, Santana L, Gold MR. Asking questions: The effect of a brief intervention in community health centers on patient activation. *Patient Educ Couns.* 2011;84(2):257–60. doi: 10.1016/j.pec.2010.07.026.
19. Rask K, Ziemer DC, Kohler SA, Hawley JN, Arinde FJ, Barnes CS. Patient activation is associated with healthy behaviors and ease in managing diabetes in an indigent population. *Diabetes Educ.* 2009;35(4):622–30. doi: 10.1177/0145721709335004.
20. Hibbard JH, Mahoney ER, Stock R, Tusler M. Do increases in patient activation result in improved self-management behaviors? *Health Serv Res.* 2007;42(4):1443–63. doi: 10.1111/j.1475-6773.2006.00669.x.